

TASKS TO ENHANCE WRITING SKILL

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Abstract: This paper describes writing activities that can be incorporated into classes to enhance students' writing ability. The author reviewed relevant literature to explore writing tasks to help students and teachers use in their endeavors to better command writing.

Keywords: writing, tasks, activities, testing, assessment

Writing is a complex process with many challenging features which all students struggle to learn and for teachers it makes them think of ways to best teach their students.

Alimov (2018) suggested five step-by-step method, which can improve students' English language writing competence. He created five steps of shaping students' writing speech: 1) preparation mode: gathering materials, setting goals, and tasks 2) exercising making sentences about the topic with the help of cluster 3) expressing your ideas in clear and logical way 4) encouraging critical thinking 5) revising, reviewing and rewriting based on the comments and feedback (Alimov, 2018)

Apart from the activities mentioned by Alimov (2018), it is commonly believed to practice composing a variety of tasks that can help students enhance their writing. The following activities can be incorporated into writing classes after some skills are practiced.

Essays or projects

Requesting students to compose essays or create projects tend to be a great method to provide an opportunity to summarize or apply what they have learned during a unit of study. In classrooms with language focus, the former types of assignments necessitate students to showcase their ability to use language structures or specific vocabulary in an authentic task.

Here is an instance that requires to provide arguments and use the future tense. Students are asked to read articles that state a position or express opinions and conduct mock debates. In the final examination, they produce an argumentative essay in which they stand on the use of mobile phones in the classroom. They should choose *for* or *against*, and argue three potential advantages or results using the future tense and the *IF, then* sentence structure. In their essays, they also incorporate related vocabulary such as *pro, con, disadvantage, benefit, and drawback*. This assignment can also be implemented into the classroom as a project like making a poster or brochure with their positions indicated (Djumabaeva, 1999).

Presentations, speeches, skits, or commercials

Presentations, speeches, skits, or commercials are creative tasks because learners can put their performative ability into practice what they have learned in the classroom. They make teachers' job easier to identify students who are good at speaking or performing a particular task. These tasks tend to be less organized meaning they do not require students to focus on regulations rather encourage creative freedom to showcase their ability. Additionally, students love to watch their friends act. So, students are much more interested in attending actively in such activities as well as the presenters who enjoy performing these tasks. Doing these tasks allow students to perceive and analyze the information as a performer and perceiver which they may not experience by just submitting their essay.

For instance, students can be assessed summatively by giving the same topic of mobile phones where they will have to argue for or against. The same requirements are applied to the task. Commercial or skit with the same requirements can be created (Bus, 2017).

Portfolios

Portfolios contain student work used to showcase students' mastery of subject comprehension. They are: class work, homework, assessment tasks, student peer assessments, or learner self-assessments.

Some portfolios aim to show student performance growth. For instance, students with less successful assignments can be replaced with more successful assignments. The purpose of this type of portfolio is to show that the students' understanding of content has increased over time. A pre and posttest approach can be applied to check how much students are performing overtime. In this way, students can benefit from seeing their improvement.

Sometimes instructors request students to describe every item in a portfolio or even reflect about how a piece of work showcases their learning or performance growth. This can be accomplished with any kind of portfolio. Some model questions for learners to answer can be like this:

- How did the task made you show your comprehension of the term or topic?
- If you have a problem with this task, what is the level of your understanding of this task now? What would you do to accomplish it in a different way?
- How do you think the work you collected showcase that you did improve your comprehension of the theme overtime? (Djumabaeva, 1999).

Business writing

Determined and committed teachers are needed to teach writing to learners and professionals who study English for Specific Purposes. "Teachers' responsibility is to identify ESP student specific needs in writing and draw attention to their academic or professional requirements regarding the particular skill. By learning students'

needs, teachers will know what materials that he/she should use in class”. Instructors will also be able to orient the writing tasks towards their level of language knowledge and proficiency. Another vital issue in instructing writing to ESP students is the teacher’s perspective about writing. Different ESP teachers treat writing in various ways. The social-constructionist method tends to be a better choice to improve business writing as it involves learners to follow a sample to help them with vocabulary, grammar and organization of a document, after that it enables to express ideas through offering a variety of patterns of composing it from draft to final product and ultimately it needs to be in accordance with the standards of the discourse community, if academic or professional (Manjola, 2015)

In addition, if our goal is to help students be competent business writers and professional in writing, communicative writing tasks should be implemented to help students expose as much as possible to reflect in their current or future jobs. English teachers who teach ESP writing have to include in their curricula all the written texts that business students are assigned to do in their respective duties. The writing tasks practiced in the classroom have to be taken from real life situations and business environment, leaving aside abstract and non-authentic tasks that they may never face in their daily routine (Manjola, 2015)

To conclude, it is very important to know the purpose of our tests, determine whether we are assessing for learning or after learning, which helps teachers determine what is next. The writing activities suggested above can also be used to assess student’s knowledge of what had been taught during the semester or academic year. Assessment can be implemented to test students’ abilities and their enhance their writing ability through in-depth timely and continuous feedback (Axmadjonov, 2017).

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